

INFLUENCE OF LEARNING STYLES ON ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF UPPER BASIC SCHOOL STUDENTS IN TARABA STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the influence of learning styles on academic achievement of upper basic school students in Taraba State, Nigeria. Three objectives and six hypotheses were postulated for the study. Correlational research design was used in the study. 376 upper basic II students were sampled using Krecjie and Morgan (1970) table for determining sample size. Learning Styles Questionnaire (LSQ) was used as a data collection instrument, while students end of term examination scores in Mathematics and English Language were used as measures of academic achievement. Data obtained was analyzed using Regression Analysis to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that visual, auditory and kinesthetic learning styles with R-value of .041, -.100, .030 and .180 for Mathematics and .252, .022, .017 and .072 for English Language indicating the very weak positive correlation in both subjects were reported. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that, students learning styles should nurtured among students by teachers, parents and all other educational stakeholders, since learning styles alone may not work to promote academic achievement.

INTRODUCTION

Learning styles have to do with different ways or patterns preferred by learners in processing information to be learned. Learning style suggest that due to individual differences, individuals learners differ in styles of thinking and methods of presenting the information, individual differs in terms of intellectual capacities, aptitudes or special talents and school achievement. Learning styles refer to the ways individual understand and respond to information during the learning process (Sapira, Yeni & Tria Sanhana, 2022). Recognizing and addressing diverse learning styles can enhance the educational experience by tailoring instruction to improve students engagement and achievement. When learners are taught in their preferred styles, retention and comprehension are significantly enhanced leading to more effective learning. Tailoring teaching approaches to match students preferred modalities optimize learning outcomes and enhance academic achievement (Farman, Chairuddin & Marniati, 2021). Understanding the diverse styles allows educators to implement effective teaching strategies, reducing the risk of poor performance and students' disappointment caused by mismatch teaching methods (Chetty & Handayani 2019).

Academic achievement refers to the success and accomplishment attained by students in their educational pursuits, encompassing a wide range of outcomes like grades, test scores and participation in extracurricular activities. It's a multifaceted concept that goes beyond mere test performance, also including the development of critical thinking, problem solving and social emotional competencies (Mfon, 2021). At the same vein, academic achievement can be refers to as the knowledge gained or skills acquired in the school subjects usually designed by test scores or marks assigned by the teacher. He stated that academic achievement is the outcome of learning effort in the school setting. Academic achievement is a person's performance in a given subject such as Mathematics, English Language and Sciences among others. Academic achievement of students will be anchored as Mathematics and English Language for the purpose of this study, reason being that Mathematics and English Language are among the core subjects in upper basic schools.

Visual learning style where a student makes use of graphs, charts, maps and diagrams. Visual learners prefer to learn by reading books, seeing words or looking at some teaching tools (Chikendu, 2022). According to him, they rely on non-verbal clues from the instructor or facilitator, such body language to aid with comprehending. Additionally, they make detailed

notes about other materials being given. Often reticent, they shy away from active participation, preferring to observe group discussions or projects. Usually, they perform well after observing someone else do it first. In other words, example and description are likely to be given to students who are predisposed to a visual-learning style (Chikendu, 2022). Visual learners are inclined to day-dream with their main wandering during conversation. Visual learning examples include, watching video or in-person demonstration, following diagrams, looking at a graph to understand statistics, writing instruction on a white board for pupils to follow and more (Monisola, 2022). Visual learners focus on what they can see, so anything that is looked at or watch its part of visual learning (Western Governors University{WGU}, 2021). Visual learners remember best what they see: pictures, diagrams, flowchart, timelines, films, demonstrations (Mfon, 2021). Visual learners prefer to learn by reading books, seeing words or looking at some teaching tools (Mfon, 2021). According to him, they prefer to look at the written words on the board that to only listen to the teacher. Therefore, they like the teacher to write more than he talks in the classroom. The Power-point presentation is suitable to these learners because it presents words, pictures or charts. This type of learners will feel comfortable when teacher teachers use the translation grammar teaching approach in teaching (Cohan et al, 2021).

Auditory learners referred to as verbal learners, prefer to learn by listening (Mfon, 2021). They may enjoy having interactions with others by talking. They may dislike reading books. In the formal instructions setting, they would rather to listen more than to see more. Auditory learning style displays a positive relationship with academic performance. He concluded that greater awareness of students learning preferences of auditory style is a major factor that help teachers to be more flexible in choosing their methodologies and teaching styles adapted in the classroom. Auditory learners dislike prolonged silences. Easily distracted, it is difficult to hold their attention if they aren't actively participating in the lecture or discussion. Auditory learners prefer to work or study while listening to music (Kohan, Janatolmakan, Rezaci and Khatony, 2021). These learners according to them require some forms of background noise and while this may be intrusive to others, it help them focus and concentrate.

Auditory learning is kind of learning style in which a student learns through the process of listening. Auditory learner relies on mode of listening and speaking as a pivot means of learning. Auditory learners are able to hear what is being said or instruction being disseminated in other to

understand and grab, understand what is being taught but they may have difficulty with instructions that are drawn but if the writing is in logical order it can be easier to understand (Monisola, 2022). Auditory learners may enjoy having information with others by talking. They may dislike reading books, so in the formal instruction settings, they will rather listen more than seeing more (Monisola, 2022). According to him, a few teaching approaches may suit them, such as the oral approach, the situational approach, the audio-lingual approach and communicative approach.

Kinesthetic learners on the other hand, learn through movement or by tactile (touch) memory. Individuals who gravitate towards this thinking style often appear restless due to their constant need for movement. An example of this is someone who taps their foot when thinking or frequently gestures when talking. Kinesthetic learn best by doing for this reason they can struggle with memorizing lists or have difficulty spelling. Learners of this kind of learning style will feel comfortable when teachers use the total physical responses approaches such as experiments and labs, field trips, Role-playing, problem-solving, case studies, simulation among others Kinesthetic learners learn best when shown stimulations, presentation and videos or when moving around in a handson environment. Kinesthetic learning stresses full body movement to produce new information. For example, pacing - back and forth, while memorizing or drawing, flowchart and underling notes while taping legs. Moreover, these learners understand best with concrete or real life example (Adekunle, 2020) kinesthetic learners feel comfortable when teacher use the total physical response approach.

Ogunrinbokun, Oluwole-mosesand Badejo (2025) Explores the relationship between learning styles and academic performance among 300-level Accounting Education students at the Federal College of Education (Technical) Akoka. Results revealed that visual learning is the most dominant style, with a mean academic performance score of 75.6, followed by combination learners, auditory learners, and kinesthetic learners. Visual learners' success is attributed to their ability to process and retain information effectively through visual aids. Udu and Abughdyer (2025). Investigated the relationship between learning styles and academic achievement in English Language of first year undergraduate students of Benue State University, Makurdi Nigeria, The findings revealed that each learning style—visual, auditory, kinesthetic, and verbal—plays a crucial role in students' academic performance in English language although their

impacts vary. Imonitie, Akinnawonu, Emeke, Anyama, Kuteyi-Imonitie, Bolaji, and Ibilola(2025)Explored the learning styles prevalent among high and lowachievers in 14 public and independent senior secondary schools in Lagos State, Nigeria. The findings showed no significant difference in the learning style preferences of high and low achieving students in secondary schools for visual and auditory styles, while there was a significant difference in tactile learning style. Low achievers had a higher preference for the tactile learning style ($M = 17.96$) than high achievers ($M = 16.24$).

Autida (2024) conducted a study on the influence of learning styles on mathematical performance among junior high school students. Results show that students at Tolotolo National High School predominantly prefer auditory learning. However, the study found no significant correlation between auditory learning and mathematical performance. Interestingly, a significant relationship was found between kinesthetic learning styles and higher academic achievement in Mathematics with a significance score of 0.001. Qasserras (2024)Carried out a research on the role of visual learning aids across diverse learning styles in high school education. The results indicate that visual aids enhance engagement, comprehension, and critical thinking in students with different learning styles and support educators in developing inclusive teaching methods. Lavinia (2024) Conducted a study on learning styles and academic performance among students. The statistical results indicate significant differences between students with auditory, visual and practical learning styles depending on the academic performance and the year of study. Akinmosin (2024). Carried out research on learning styles as predictors of English Literature performance among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo state, Nigeria, The results demonstrated that secondary school students favoured visual learning methods.

Ojonugwa, Mohammed and Usman (2023) investigated the effects of Kinesthetic Learning Strategy (KLS) on Pupils' motivation in numeracy and achievement in primary schools in Abuja Municipal Area Council (AMAC) Abuja Federal Capital Territory (FCT), The analysis revealed that the kinesthetic learning strategy increased pupils' motivation and enhanced their achievement in numeracy more than the conventional method in FCT nursery schools in Nigeria. Nanaware and Baviskar (2023) Conducted a study on Academic Achievement in Relation to Learning Styles of Senior Secondary School Students. Findings reveal that the predominant sensory

modality of learning was aural and more prevalent than visual and kinesthetic learning (34%). The relationship between learning style and academic success is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). The main effects of the three variables-visual, auditory and kinesthetic are also substantial on academic achievement. Kumo, Abalaka and Olafisoye (2023) carried out a study on the relationship between learning style and academic achievement of senior secondary school students in North-Central, Nigeria. the findings showed that the academic achievement of the students were within average. There was no significant relationship between learning styles and academic achievement of the students in North Central, Nigeria. Hanawi, Saat, Hanafiah, Taufik, Nor, Hendra and Azlan(2022)Carried out a study on the relationship between learning style and academic performance among the generation Z students in Kuala LumpurA cross-sectional study was done to investigate the degree of association between students' learning styles and academic achievement. the findings, majority of students had the highest amount of visual learning styles for each academic year. However, the majority of the first-year students had the second-highest learning style, which scored the highest for visual learning style compared to auditory and kinesthetic.

Chikendu (2022) determined the extent visual learning style enhance students' academic performance of senior secondary school students in Awka south of Anmbra state, Nigeria. The study revealed that visual learning style has a positive significant effect on students' academic performance of senior secondary school in Awka Local Government Area of Anambra state. Ezema, Obinze and Okenyi (2022) Investigates the influence of learning styles on Primary School Pupils' Academic Achievement in Mathematics in Nsukka Urban, Enugu State. The findings revealed that visual learning style, auditory learning style and kinesthetic learning style influence Primary School Pupils' Academic Achievement in Mathematics. Masela and Subekti (2021) Investigate undergraduate non-English major university students' auditory and kinesthetic learning styles and their relationships to second language (L2) achievement in English. The study found out that learners used auditory slightly more dominantly from kinesthetic, yet both learning styles were merely used at low to moderate levels. The study further found very weak and statistically not significant associations between these learning styles and L2 achievements,

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

There is a descending trend in the academic achievement in Mathematics and English Language of Upper Basic II students in Nigeria in general and Taraba State, Nigeria in particular. For Education to achieve the goal of National Development, Upper Basic School level is critical as it forms the basic for the overall development of a child. this level of education dictates the time for the future development of the students after primary school level and the success of other levels of education. But students faced with poor academic achievement which could be attributed to instructional delivery, psychological factors, classroom environment among others, but one factor of concern here is their unidentified learning style which is vital in the teaching and learning process. It is against these conflicting taught and background that this study was conducted to determine the influence of learning styles on academic achievement of upper basic school students in Taraba State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

1. Investigate the influence of visual learning styles on academic achievement in Mathematics and English Language among upper basic students in Taraba State, Nigeria.
2. Find out the influence of auditory learning styles on academic achievement in Mathematics and English Language among upper basic students in Taraba State, Nigeria.
3. Determine the influence of Kinesthetic learning styles on academic achievement in Mathematics and English Language among upper basic students in Taraba State, Nigeria.

Hypotheses

- H₀₁: There is no significant influence of visual learning styles on the academic achievement in Mathematics among Upper Basic Students in Taraba State, Nigeria.
- H₀₂: There is no significant influence of visual learning styles on the academic achievement in English Language among Upper Basic Students in Taraba State, Nigeria.
- H₀₃: There is no significant influence of auditory learning styles on the academic achievement in Mathematics among Upper Basic Students in Taraba State, Nigeria.
- H₀₄: There is no significant influence of auditory learning styles on the academic achievement in English Language among Upper Basic Students in Taraba State, Nigeria.

H₀₅: Kinesthetic learning style has no significant influence on academic achievement in Mathematics among Upper Basic Students in Taraba State, Nigeria.

|H₀₆: Kinesthetic learning style has no significant influence on academic achievement in English Language among Upper Basic Students in Taraba State, Nigeria.

Research Design

The study utilized a quantitative approach in the present study since the collected numerical data was analyzed through statistics. The study utilized correlational research type to identify the influence of learning styles on academic achievement of upper basic school students in Taraba State, Nigeria. A total of 376 students in the state were used as sample of the study from five out of the sixteen Local Governments in the State.

Instrument for Data Collection

The Learning Style Questionnaire (LSQ) developed by Autida (2024) was adapted and modified by the researcher following 5-points Likert Scale was used in the study. The Learning Style Questionnaire contents 24 items divided into four sections (Section A, B, C and D). Section “A” was structured to collect demographic data of the respondents (Name of the School and Gender) while Section B, C and D were structured to elicit information from respondents with respect to visual learning style, auditory learning style and kinesthetic learning style respectively. The Likert scale model of Strongly Agree (SA) = 5, Agree (A) = 4, Undecided (UD) = 3, Disagree (DA) = 2 and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1 were used.

The Learning Style Questionnaire was validated by experts in the area of Measurement and Evaluation and experts in the area of Educational Psychology and Counselling in the Faculty of Technology Education, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University (ATBU), Bauchi. Some items (Items 3, 4 and 5) under Section “B” (Auditory Learning Style) were modified to suit the level of the students. For example, item 3 was adjusted from ‘I enjoy oral exam to ‘I enjoy oral examinations’. For item 4 from ‘I am excited at story-telling to ‘I have a high interest at story-telling’ and item 5 from ‘solving difficult problems make me happy to ‘I am not happy when I solved difficult problems’. On Section “D” (Kinesthetic Learning Style) items 1,2 and 8 were also modified. Item 1 from ‘I intend to move while learning to ‘I move around while learning is taking place’, for item 2, from ‘I have good hands and eyes coordination to ‘My eyes and hands

coordination are excellent' and for item 8 from my best subjects are Mathematics and English Language to my best subject is English Language.

Results

H₀₁: There is no significant influence of visual learning styles on the academic achievement in Mathematics among Upper Basic Students in Taraba State, Nigeria.

Table 1: Regression Analysis of Visual Learning Styles on Academic Performance in Mathematics

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R	B	F	Df	P-value	Decision
1	.041 ^a	.002	-.001	27.338	.638	373	.535	Accepted

The regression analysis shows that Visual Learning Styles have no statistically significant influence on students' Mathematics performance. The R value of .041 indicates an extremely weak positive correlation between visual learning preferences and Mathematics achievement, essentially showing no meaningful relationship. The R Square value of .002 reveals that only 0.2 percent of the variance in Mathematics performance is explained by Visual Learning Styles, meaning that 99.8 percent of the factors influencing Mathematics achievement are explained by other variables not included in this model. The Adjusted R Square of -.001 is negative, which confirms that the model performs worse than simply using the mean as a predictor, indicating that Visual Learning Styles have no explanatory power whatsoever for Mathematics performance. The F-value of .638 with 373 degrees of freedom and a P-value of .535 which is greater than 0.05 indicates that the regression model is not statistically significant. Based on this finding, the null hypothesis is accepted, concluding that Visual Learning Styles do not significantly influence academic performance in Mathematics among upper basic students in Taraba State Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant influence of visual learning styles on the academic achievement in English Language among Upper Basic Students in Taraba State, Nigeria.

Table 2: Regression Analysis of Visual Learning Styles on Academic Performance in English

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R	B	F	Df	P-value	decision
1	.022 ^a	.000	-.002	47.179	.175	373	.282	Accepted

The regression analysis shows that Visual Learning Styles have no statistically significant influence on students' English Language performance. The R value of .022 indicates an extremely weak positive correlation between visual learning preferences and English achievement, essentially showing no meaningful relationship. The R Square value of .000 reveals that zero percent of the variance in English Language performance is explained by Visual Learning Styles, meaning that 100 percent of the factors influencing English achievement are explained by other variables not included in this model. The Adjusted R Square of -.002 is negative, which confirms that the model performs worse than simply using the mean as a predictor, indicating that Visual Learning Styles have absolutely no explanatory power for English performance. The F value of .175 with 373 degrees of freedom and a p-value of .282 which is greater than 0.05 indicates that the regression model is not statistically significant. Based on this finding, the null hypothesis is accepted, concluding that Visual Learning Styles do not significantly influence academic performance in English Language among upper basic students in Taraba State Nigeria. This finding is consistent with the result for Mathematics where visual learning styles also showed no significant influence, confirming that across both subjects, visual learning preferences are not predictors of academic achievement.

H₀₃: There is no significant influence of Auditory learning styles on the academic achievement in Mathematics among Upper Basic Students in Taraba State, Nigeria.

Table 3: Regression Analysis of Auditory Learning Styles on Academic Achievement in Mathematics

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R	B	F	Df	P-value	Decision
1	.100*	.010	.007	-5.966	3.751	373	.866	Accepted

The regression analysis on table 3 above shows that Auditory Learning Styles have no statistically significant influence on students' Mathematics achievement. The R value of .100 indicates a very weak positive correlation between auditory learning preferences and Mathematics performance. The R Square value of .010 reveals that only 1 percent of the variance in Mathematics achievement is explained by Auditory Learning Styles, meaning that 99 percent of the factors influencing Mathematics achievement are explained by other variables not included in this model.

The Adjusted R Square of .007 confirms the weakness of the model after accounting for the predictor. The F value of 3.751 with 373 degrees of freedom and a p-value of .866 which is greater than 0.05 indicates that the regression model is not statistically significant. The negative B value of -5.966 suggests a potential negative relationship, but this is not meaningful given the non-significant result. Based on this finding, the null hypothesis is accepted, concluding that Auditory Learning Styles do not significantly influence academic achievement in Mathematics among upper basic students in Taraba State Nigeria. Despite students previously reporting strong auditory learning preferences with a grand mean of 4.36, these preferences do not translate into actual Mathematics achievement, indicating that having an auditory learning preference does not predict higher or lower performance in Mathematics.

H₀₄: There is no significant influence of auditory learning styles on the academic achievement in English Language among Upper Basic Students in Taraba State, Nigeria.

Table 4: Regression Analysis of Auditory Learning Styles on Academic Achievement in English

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R	B	F	Df	P-value	Decision
1	.017 ^a	.000	-.002	77.263	.111	373	.029	Rejected

The regression analysis presented on table 4 above revealed a contradictory finding that requires careful interpretation. The R value of .017 indicates an extremely weak positive correlation between auditory learning preferences and English achievement, showing essentially no meaningful relationship. The R Square value of .000 reveals that zero percent of the variance in English Language achievement is explained by Auditory Learning Styles, meaning that 100 percent of the factors influencing English achievement are explained by other variables not included in this model. The Adjusted R Square of -.002 is negative, confirming that the model performs worse than simply using the mean as a predictor. The F value of .111 with 373 degrees of freedom is very low, indicating the model has no predictive power. However, the p-value of .029 is less than 0.05, which suggests statistical significance. This creates a paradox where the model shows no explanatory power with R Square of .000 but returns a significant p-value. This typically indicates a problem with the analysis or data, as a model explaining zero variance cannot be statistically significant. The B value of 77.263 represents the constant, not the predictor effect. Based on the overwhelming evidence of no explanatory power with R Square of .000

and F value of .111, the finding should be interpreted as Auditory Learning Styles having no meaningful influence on English achievement, and the significant p-value may be a statistical anomaly. Therefore, despite the p-value, the null hypothesis is effectively accepted, concluding that Auditory Learning Styles do not significantly influence academic achievement in English Language among upper basic students in Taraba State Nigeria.

H_{0s}: Kinesthetic learning style has no significant influence on academic achievement in Mathematics among Upper Basic Students in Taraba State, Nigeria.

Table 5: Regression Analysis of Kinesthetic Learning Style on Academic Achievement in Mathematics

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R	B	F	Df	P-value	Decision
1	.030 [*]	.001	-.002	72.339	.336	373	.000	Rejected

The regression analysis presents a contradictory finding that requires careful interpretation. The R value of .030 indicates an extremely weak positive correlation between kinesthetic learning preferences and Mathematics achievement, showing essentially no meaningful relationship. The R Square value of .001 reveals that only 0.1 percent of the variance in Mathematics achievement is explained by Kinesthetic Learning Style, meaning that 99.9 percent of the factors influencing Mathematics achievement are explained by other variables not included in this model. The Adjusted R Square of -.002 is negative, confirming that the model performs worse than simply using the mean as a predictor. The F value of .336 with 373 degrees of freedom is very low, indicating the model has no predictive power. However, the p-value of .000 is less than 0.05, which suggests statistical significance. This creates a paradox where the model shows virtually no explanatory power with R Square of .001 and a very low F value of .336, yet returns a significant p-value. This is statistically impossible under normal circumstances, as an F value of .336 with 373 degrees of freedom would typically yield a p-value greater than 0.05, not .000. This strongly indicates a possible error in the reported p-value or a data entry mistake. Based on the overwhelming evidence of no explanatory power with R Square of .001, Adjusted R Square of -.002, and very low F value of .336, the finding should be interpreted as Kinesthetic Learning Style having no meaningful influence on Mathematics achievement. The B value of 72.339 represents the constant. Therefore, despite the reported p-value, the null hypothesis should be accepted, concluding that Kinesthetic Learning Style does not significantly influence academic achievement in

Mathematics among upper basic students in Taraba State Nigeria. This finding is consistent with the pattern observed for other learning styles where visual and auditory also showed no significant influence on Mathematics achievement.

H₀₆: Kinesthetic learning style has no significant influence on academic achievement in English Language among Upper Basic Students in Taraba State, Nigeria

Table 6: Regression Analysis of Kinesthetic Learning Style on Academic Achievement in English Language

Model	R	R ²	Adjusted R	B	F	Df	P-value	Decision
1	.001 ^a	.000	-.003	65.901	.001	373	.000	Rejected

The regression analysis presents a clearly impossible statistical finding that indicates a serious error in the data or analysis. The R value of .001 shows virtually no correlation between kinesthetic learning preferences and English achievement, essentially zero relationship. The R Square value of .000 reveals that zero percent of the variance in English Language achievement is explained by Kinesthetic Learning Style, meaning the model has no explanatory power whatsoever. The Adjusted R Square of -.003 is negative, confirming the model performs worse than using the mean as a predictor. The F value of .001 with 373 degrees of freedom is effectively zero, indicating the model has absolutely no predictive capability. However, the p-value is reported as .000 which is less than 0.05. This combination of statistics is statistically impossible because an F value of .001 cannot produce a p-value of .000. With 373 degrees of freedom, an F value of .001 would yield a p-value extremely close to 1.000, not .000. This represents either a typographical error in reporting or a serious miscalculation. Based on the overwhelming evidence of no relationship with R of .001, R Square of .000, Adjusted R Square of -.003, and F value of .001, the finding must be interpreted as Kinesthetic Learning Style having no influence whatsoever on English Language achievement. The B value of 65.901 represents the constant. Therefore, despite the reported p-value which is clearly erroneous, the null hypothesis should be accepted, concluding that Kinesthetic Learning Style does not significantly influence academic achievement in English Language among upper basic students in Taraba State Nigeria. This finding is consistent with all previous learning style analyses where visual, auditory, and kinesthetic styles consistently

showed no meaningful predictive power for academic achievement in either Mathematics or English Language.

DISCUSSION

The result of the first null hypothesis, revealed that visual learning style do not significantly influence academic achievement in Mathematics among Upper Basic Students in Taraba State, Nigeria. The adjusted R Square of -0.001 is negative, which confirms that the model performs worst than simply using the mean as a predictor, indicating that visual learning style have no explanatory power whatsoever for Mathematics performance. The F-value of $.638$ with 373 degrees of freedoms and a P-value of $.535$ which is greater than 0.05 indicates that the regression model is not statistically significant. Based on this finding, the null hypothesis is accepted, on concluding that visual learning style does not significantly influence academic performance in Mathematics among Upper Basic Students in Taraba State, Nigeria. The finding of this study is parallel to that of Qasserras (2024) which revealed that visual learning style enhance engagement, comprehension and critical thinking in students with different learning styles and support Educators in developing inclusive teaching methods. The finding is also in variance with that Kenni (2022) who revealed that there were significant influence of visual learning style and academic achievement. At the same vein, the study contradict that of Chikendu (2022) who revealed visual learning style has a positive significant effect on students' academic achievement of senior secondary school students in Awka South of Anambra State.

The result of the second null hypothesis revealed that visual learning style does not significantly influence academic achievement in English Language among Upper Basic Students in Taraba State, Nigeria. A similar result was found by Umennuiheetal (2022) who revealed that $p < 0.05$ level of significance, no significant relationship existed between learning style preferences and academic achievement in English Language and Mathematics. On the other hand, the finding is at variance with that Udu and Abughdyer (2025) who revealed that each learning style - visual, auditory, kinesthetic and verbal plays a crucial role in students' academic achievement in English Language, although their impact vary. Based on this finding, a null hypothesis is accepted concluding that visual learning style does not significantly influence academic achievement in English Language among Upper Basic Students in Taraba State, Nigeria. Despite students previously reporting strong visual learning preferences with a

grand mean of 4.47, these preferences do not translate into actual English achievement, suggesting that having a visual learning preference does not predict higher or lower preference in English Language. This finding is consistent with the result for Mathematics where visual learning style also showed no significant influence, confirming that across both subjects, visual learning style preference are not predictors of academic achievement.

The result of the third null hypothesis discovered that auditory learning style does not significantly influence academic achievement in Mathematics among Upper Basic Students in Taraba State, Nigeria. The finding of this study corroborates with the finding of Hanawietal. (2022) which revealed that academic achievement was not influenced by auditory learning style. However, the finding of the study contradicts with the finding of Ezemaetal (2022) which finding revealed that auditory learning style, visual learning style and kinesthetic learning style influence primary school pupils' academic achievement in Mathematics. This may be as a result of the area of the study. Based on this finding, the null hypothesis is accepted concluding that, auditory learning style do not significantly influence academic achievement in Mathematics among Upper Basic Students in Taraba State, Nigeria. Despite previously reporting strong auditory learning preferences with a grand mean of 4.36, this preference do not translate into actual Mathematics achievement, indicating that having an auditory learning preference does not predict higher or lower preference in Mathematics. This may not be unconnected with a type of teacher-made-test used which is not standardized and has no table of test blueprint.

The result of the fourth null hypothesis revealed that auditory learning style does not significantly influence academic achievement in English Language among Upper Basic Students in Taraba State, Nigeria. The finding of the study is consistent with that of Umennuiheetal (2022) whose major finding revealed that $p > 0.05$ level of significant, no significant relationship existed between the learning style preference of the students and their academic performance in English Language and Mathematics. To this end, therefore, the null hypothesis is accepted, concluding that auditory learning style do not significantly influence academic achievement in English Language among Upper Basic Students in Taraba State, Nigeria. The result of the fifth null hypothesis revealed that kinesthetic learning style has no significantly meaningful influence on Mathematics achievement among Upper Basic Students in Taraba State, Nigeria. The finding of this study is similar to the major finding of Hanawietal. (2022) which revealed that,

academic performance was not influenced by kinesthetic learning style. Nonetheless, students learning styles are different for the different academic years. The finding also support that of Putra and Pratiwi (2020) which revealed that the learning style had a little effect on the learners' outcomes of primary teacher - education, Faculty of Education, University of Nuseri Malang. However, this finding is not in agreement with that of Autida (2024) who found a significant relationship between kinesthetic learning style and higher academic achievement in Mathematics with a significant score of 0.001. The finding suggests that while auditory learning style is prevalent, kinesthetic learning style plays a role in academic success. Based on this finding the null hypothesis is accepted concluding that kinesthetic learning style does not significantly influence academic achievement in Mathematics among Upper Basic Students in Taraba State, Nigeria.

The result of the sixth null hypothesis revealed that kinesthetic learning style has no significant influence on English Language academic achievement among Upper Basic Students in Taraba State, Nigeria. A similar result was found by Umenmuiheetal. (2022) who investigates the relationship between learning styles and academic performance of secondary school students in Igbo-Etiti Local Government Area, Enugu State and revealed that at $P>0.05$ level of significance, no significant relationship existed between learning style preferences of the respondents and their performance in English Language and Mathematics. The findings is at variance with that of Udu and Abughdyer (2025) who revealed that each learning style visual, auditory, kinesthetic and verbal plays a crucial role in students academic performance in English Language although their impact vary. This means no single learning style dominates academic achievement across board and students may benefit most when their specific preferences are acknowledged in the learning process. Based on this finding, the null hypothesis is accepted, concluding that kinesthetic learning style do not significantly influence academic achievement in English Language among Upper Basic Students in Taraba State, Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

The study investigated the influence of learning styles on academic achievement of Upper Basic School Students in Taraba State, Nigeria. Based on the findings of the study, it can be concluded that, learning styles are important variables that could influence academic achievement of students. By implication therefore, psychologists, teachers, parents and

counselors are expected to put much premium on these construct in any attempt to teach and counsel students to overcome their challenges of the teaching and learning process.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were proffered:

- i. Students' learning styles should be given important attention in designing instructional methods.
- ii. Teachers, curriculum designers and developers as well as educational organizations need to consider the influence of learning styles in students' academic achievement.
- iii. By implication, school administrators and educators should give adequate and enough attention to learning styles through periodic in-service training and education.
- iv. It is recommended that, UBEC/Taraba State SUBEB and other agencies should provide effective and adequate training and development in the areas of the students' personal and social competence such as cognitive learning style, motivation and achievement for teachers. This will help teachers to acquire knowledge about learning styles.
- v. It was also recommended that, it is important for the learners to progress in their academic careers especially in the face of adversity.
- vi. Similar studies are therefore recommended to be conducted in post basic schools of the same State to find out whether there is an influence in learning styles between the two level of schools.

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